

Title :

The impact of social media on
academics in the UAE

Aisha Ahmed Alyammahi

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Abstract

The given study helps in identifying the relationship between the impact of social media and academics in the UAE. For this, the study involves a descriptive research design and involves data that has been collected and analyzed with the help of regression analysis, with the tables reflecting the data. Since the test follows a singular form of data, the results are not specified. The given study uses a hypothesis to explain and prove the relationship between the same. As per the findings of the study, there is a need for developing a better sense of AI proceedings with an eye on the possibilities.

Topic selection:

My research topic is about The impact of social media on academics in the UAE. I chose to write about this topic because of the enormous social media usage these days. Social media has become a big part of our lives, which might not be suitable for the younger generation. I believe that social media use has a negative impact on academics, such as decreased grades. Also, it can contribute to cyberbullying in school and young people's physical health because many are addicted to their phones. So, I am worried about its negative effect on UAE students. As a mother and a teacher, I have to make society aware of the impact of social media on students and the community. So, I decided to do this study.

Introduction: -

Today we live in the social media era. Social media has become a part of our daily lives. People communicate virtually more than the real life. Moreover, The social sphere has migrated further away from the body due to technological advancements and changes, grown enormous, and begun to coexist with nature as a more developed social creature. (bilici & yildirim, 2021) In

brief, social media can be defined as a multitude of internet- and network-based technologies that enable asynchronous and multidimensional information exchange, communication, and activity engagement can be referred to as social media. The phrase "the form of media that is built on communication and interaction amongst people online" can also describe social media. Younus, K. (2018). Furthermore, Social networking services (SNS) have evolved from being purely hedonistic for personal use to being intense hierarchical apparatuses for internal and external correspondence and cooperative efforts with many stakeholders. Today, social networking is a common practice, especially among young students. Online networking is becoming increasingly popular, which signifies that technology is essential to today's pupils. Ahmed et al. (2018). While there are numerous advantages to social media, including the potential for students to express themselves creatively, educational possibilities, and interpersonal connections, on the other hand, social media also impacts students' mental health, including their emotional, psychological, and social well-being. One may argue that because university students use social media so regularly during the day and at night, it dramatically impacts their everyday life. However, despite the significant contributions these technologies have made to knowledge acquisition, it is essential to evaluate whether they are being used for learning-related goals or for other tasks that run the risk of technological misuse. Kolhar et al. (2021). Previous studies were conducted to investigate the impact of social media on the student. As (Ahmed, Dar, Tahir, & Masood, 2018) showed a study looking into how social media affects students' academic performance. According to the survey, most candidates had cell phones with internet access and were familiar with various social media platforms. A study has shown that heavy social media use impacted academic achievement. Social media websites are relatively helpful; from what I've seen, they help students make new friends and relieve some academic strain. In addition, there is an overwhelming consensus

among academics that social media tools have the potential to shift academic studies and teaching practice into new directions. Some scholars argue that social media are already having a transformative impact on how we communicate, organize, and share information. Therefore, the main problem in my research is the increasing use of social networking sites by students during their studies which leads to a lack of attention to their lessons and causes concern about their performance. Further, it is essential to find the answer to this research question in my study:

-What is the purpose of students using social media?

-How long do they use it during the day?

-What is social media's effect on the student's performance?

To Acknowledge that my study is a replication of an existing study on the topic of the Influence of social media on students' academic achievement conducted by these Authors:1- Basil C.E. Oguguo , 2-Juliet O. Ajuonuma , 3-Roseline Azubuike , 4-Catherine U. Ene , Florence O. 5- Atta , 6-Chidimma J. Oko in Nigeria. Therefore, My main research paper aims to examine how social media is used, the time students spend on social media, the perception, and its effect on the academic performance of college students in the UAE. The topic of social media usage and its effect on students' achievement is essential because of the increase of this habit nowadays. The study is considered very valuable because it will contribute to educational decision-makers deciding how they deal with the fact that students using social media either prevent it or enroll in educational programs.

Literature review

This is the second part of the research to conduct a literature review, create a theoretical framework, and propose hypotheses. According to a study by Jesson(2011), When completing a literature review for an academic assignment, you can demonstrate that you understand and comprehend what is already known and eventually identify inconsistencies and holes in the area of research. Therefore, reviewing previous studies about the social media aspects and what affects student performance will strengthen the theories in my research. This part is organized as

- ❖ Reviewing literature about Academics performance, the term social media, the usage of social media, the duration of Students spent on social media, the frequency of using social media, and the student perception of social media.
- ❖ Hypotheses
- ❖ Theoretical model of the study.

Previous studied answered the most frequent questions about the relationship between social media and students as seen below.

What is the purpose of students using social media?

The digital age has led a majority of the students to shift their regular lifestyle processes through the lanes of the social media world. However, there is a section of people who still believe that social media usage deteriorates the tools of academics for the students and their learning process (Lacka & Wong, 2021). A section of students in the UAE prefers to obtain new information from websites for their academic implementations. However, a large portion of the students keep in touch with their family and friends through social media, due to the distance learning process they are involved in.

How long do they use it during the day?

According to the study by Hussain, Ahmed, Hamid, Tuffaha & Aguilar (2020), more than 50% of the 13-15 years age group and 63% of the age group of 16-17 spend as much as 3 hours on average on the internet, web portals and social media platforms. Thus, a reflection of the growing nature of the social media section is visibly seen in adolescents and children from these age groups.

What is the common social media they use?

Students of the millennial era prefer to majorly use Whatsapp, Instagram, LinkedIn, Snapchat, google plus or youtube services (Bajpai,2018).

What is social media's effect on the student's performance?

As per Cao & Tian (2022), tests made on the 256 responses received in the study findings imitate an answer of collaborative learning process more student-instructor interaction and academic distractions are empirical pieces of evidence of the latest study process.

Academic performance

Academic achievement is a term for performance outcomes that describe how well a person performed in activities that were the subject of instruction, particularly in school, college, and university settings. Oxford Bibliographies, (2020)

In fact, the Student's academic performance can be influenced by lots of factors. According to research from Al-Rahmi et al.(2015) instructors and mentors who include social media in their teaching strategies can help students and researchers perform better academically. The results demonstrated that social media encourages collaborative learning and participation, which

enhances students' academic achievement. Other researchers' observations showed that pupils `persists, it will negatively impact their academic performance and general prospects. Apraku et al.,(2019)

social media

Even though the word "social media" has gained popularity in academic and popular discourse, has been used to refer to a wide range of unrelated concepts. Social media is frequently regarded as a platform that encourages engagement and information sharing.Steenkamp&Hyde-Clarke (2014) Additionally, many internet- and network-based technologies that enable asynchronous and multidimensional information exchange, communication, and activity engagement can be referred to as social media. Social media is also described as "the form of media built on online dialogue and engagement amongst users.³Another author stated that although the term social media has become widespread in academic and popular discourse, the notion has been used to describe various and somewhat different ideas. Social media is often considered a platform that facilitates information sharing and participation. Ariel &Avidar (2015)

The usage of social media

People can communicate with one another through social media.¹ Additionally, it enables users to create, access, share, and interact with the available online content. Bhandarkar et al.(2012)

Many studies investigate the student usage of social media, and there is an argument about whether social media has positive or negative effects on student performance. In particular, This study investigated if social media usage and social media multitasking among university students affect academic achievement. The use of social media for education was investigated in this study, and it was discovered that it was not a reliable indicator of academic performance as

measured by cumulative grade point average. However, social media use for non-academic purposes (primarily video gaming) and social media multitasking significantly negatively influenced academic performance. Lau (2017). On the other hand, students use social media for educational reasons to communicate with their professors and among themselves for peer-to-peer interactions. In addition to using it as a communication tool, they also used social media to advance their academic work and comprehend what they had been taught in class. Additionally, using social media for class-related research has improved students' grades. Overall, using social media had a favorable impact on students' GPA. Sutarno (2019)

H1: The usage of social media influences academic performance.

The duration of using the social media

A study was conducted by M. Talaue et al. (2018) to examine the time students spent on social media applications. The results show that social media has taken over students' lives and consumes most of their free time. The respondents' time spent on social media emphasized that it affected their academic achievement. The results show that (38.3 percent) of internet users report spending an average of 4-6 hours per day on social media. Also (28.3 percent) report spending 1-3 hours; (26.7 percent) report spending more than 6 hours online, and (6.7 percent) report not knowing how much time they spend online for social media. Most respondents use social media between 4-6 hours daily.

Besides, Social media usage duration has been investigated. When comparing daily social media use to academic performance status (high performers vs. low performers), it was found that 51.3% of high performers and 61.2 % of low performers used social media for longer than three hours daily. Compared to high performers, low performers use social media more often. Bhandarkar et al (2021)

H2: The duration spent on social media influences Student's academic performance.

The student perception of social media

College students value social media as a tool for everyday use and have a favorable opinion of its use for learning. The study's findings indicated that participants spent a lot of time on social media, and it may be inferred that using social media for learning may improve motivation or performance. The impact of social media on students' perceptions of their academic learning throughout the coursework. (Alhababi, Alfadil, Alzamanan, & Williams, 2015) According to Samed Al-Adwan et al.(2020) his research findings show that perceptions of social media usefulness positively impact the Student who uses it in learning. Additionally, they use social media for collaborative learning, improved communication, enjoyment, and ease of use; resource sharing has a negligible impact on this use, and social media use positively impacts students' perceptions of their academic performance.

H3: The Student's perception of social media influences academic performance.

Hypothesis: -

- H1: The usage of social media influences the Student's academic performance.
- H2: The duration spent on social media influences the Student's academic performance
- H3: The Student's perception of social media influences academic performance.

Theoretical framework: -

A theoretical framework for this study was conceptualized based on the hypotheses mentioned above, supported by the evaluated literature. As seen in Figure 1. The dependent variable is the student performance affected by the independent variables of social media: the usage of social media, the duration student, spend on social media, and the student perceptions of social media.

Figure 1: The Theoretical Framework

Research methodology

Background information and relevant issues

Social media in contemporary times offer a variety of services to individuals, based on their needs and type of usage. In the UAE population, the majority of people use social media this population most of them are students. This platform helps people to keep going through the pandemic. Students are spending an average of 3 hours per day on social media. At present days social media user is increasing day by day, most people use social media and it has become almost a habit for people. The use of social media platforms in the academic perspective has grown significantly. Advanced technology and information have enabled social media use in the academic sector. Social media helps to increase the learning process from a teacher-centered to a student-centered approach. People between the age of 16-25 years age considered active users of social media (Jenaibi & Mansoori, 2022). UAE is considered the technological hub in the Middle East. Establishing a learning system through social media required minimal resources. Social media creates an opportunity for educational purposes through the e-learning system and this help the students to learn all the things through the internet. Social media is a dynamic tool for

exploring the teaching process, this platform help student to gain interest in an academic perspective, provide group discussion and exchange idea with each other and improve their learning process, Therefore social media decreases students' academic performances because they spent much time on social media chatting and making friends. The digital age has led a majority of the students to shift their regular lifestyle processes through the lanes of the social media world.

There is some issue that social media have that this platform distract students from their goal which help them to achieve their future career growth. Social media itself is not a problem it is the way how people used this platform. Thus, a reflection of the growing nature of the social media section is visibly seen in adolescents and children from these age groups. Lack of privacy and confidentiality is the most important issue on this topic. Disclosing secrets relating to people's private life, without that person's consent, can attract liability under the Penal Code and the Cyber Crimes Law. Discloser of personal information such as people's employment information and personal information is attracting the UAE legal liability. Cyberbullying is also one of the main issues of social media. Social media help for making friends but this platform also helps cruel people to tear into others with little effort.

Developed questionnaire

The questionnaire has been developed keeping in mind some of the important metrics used in the study and the questionnaire helps in serving the purpose of the said objectives. The first objective is the usage of social media by students. This will take up questions 1-9 and will refer to the academic performance of the student. The duration of social media use will form a basis for questions 10 to 16. The perception associated with the use of social media by the students will form the basis of the last question.

In this study, research 32 students both males and females to understand the impact of social media on students academic performances. At the time of development of the questionnaire, research determines some factors that help to understand the research process. Those factors are what is the purpose of the students using social media, and how frequently students have uploaded their personal information and their picture on social media. The time of engagement in social media is a week and day by day. How does social media help to understand the learning process and how does this enhance the students interest, at last, how does social media have a negative or positive impact on students academic performances.

Sampling process

The sampling process is involved in the statistical analysis that is predetermined by a number of observations taken from the population. In this research, they take students to understand the social media impact on their education. The sampling process is one of the important parts of research it consists of a group of people, an objective which is taken from a larger population to measure. The sample is representative of the population. The sampling technique involves selecting individual members of the population which make statistical interference. This is an identification process of a particular data which is selected for data collection. Sampling is mainly two types that are probability sampling and non-probability sampling. In probability sampling, there are simple random sampling, stratified sampling, cluster random sampling, and systematic random sampling. And in non-probability sampling convenience sampling, judgmental sampling, snowball sampling, and quota sampling. In this research, they take probability sampling through random sampling, this sampling method is one of the best sampling methods this help to save resources and time. It is a reliable process of gathering information

where every student in the population gets an equal chance to select. In simple random sampling, a researcher selects the target population and removes sampling bias.

In the given study, hypothesis has been tested by using two of the main hypotheses, which includes two of the main variables: one independent and other dependent. The use of social media is independent variable, whereas the academic performance of the students is dependent variable used for testing out the hypotheses.

This research has taken 32 students in both male and female groups and in this research 7 males and 25 females have been selected. Therefore most females spent their time on social media compared to male students. To select the sample first identify the population from where they collected data, then decided the sample size, they need to decide the number of samples in the research. Randomly selected the sample so that everyone gets an equal chance for participating in this research.

Data collection methodology

Data is collected in the form of facts, figures, objectives, and symbols that help to understand the research success through valid data. Data collection is mainly two types that are primary data collection and secondary data collection. Primary data collection is a type of information that is acquired directly from the first-hand source through various processes are surveys, questionnaires, observation, and interviews (Menggala et al., 2021). Primary data collection consists mainly of two types: quantitative data collection methods and qualitative data collection methods. Quantitative data collection methods depend on mathematical calculations using multiple forms like correlation and regression and close-end questions and so on (Ilic, 2019). Qualitative data collection methods do not involve mathematical calculation as it is involved in quantifying the data. At the time of data collection, qualitative data collection methods through

observation, questionnaires, case studies and so on. In the secondary data collection process, it has been observed that primary data was collected previously by a particular researcher and the findings of the same were used by other researchers to support their research process. In secondary data the information is already available on the internet and secondary research work is to analyse this data on the basis of the topic. The secondary data are two types which are published data and unpublished data. Considering the benefit of the primary data collection process this research paper has considered acquiring the needed data from a primary source by undertaking a survey. In this research, they take primary data collection through quantitative data collection methods. Through questionnaires, the researcher collects data and understands the research progress.

Questionnaire methods design a set of questions that are responses to the research subjects. In there no negative marking is present, subjects are only provided two or three options that are “yes”, “no”, “cannot understand” or “true” or “false”. The subject is given the answer according to their knowledge and their perspective and the current situation of their life. They only read, answered and returned the questionnaire (Wu, Lu, Sabharwal & Mottaghi, 2022, June). This help to understand the definite order of the from the same. A successful questionnaire survey should contain some specific points that are short and simple, provide a logical sequence, give proper space for answers, use simple language so that everyone can understand. There are some benefits to the questionnaire that are less costly, it is the best method for collecting data from a wide population and this allows nationwide or even international coverage.

The given study uses quantitative data analysis which is represented by using tables. The form of analysis used here includes regression analysis for the data given. A questionnaire will be helpful in the given study for connecting with multiple people from a research perspective. For this, the

data collected involves practical data and has been used for developing a connection with the same. For collecting the replies, the Likert scale has been used, which helps in collecting answers through multiple answers which helps in analyzing the results and representing the level of emotional responses associated with it. For testing the hypothesis for the use of social media by students, the regression analysis has been used and the tables reflect the data associated with the regression analysis. The research design involved in the study is a descriptive research design, which is used for describing the relationship between the dependent and independent variables of the study.

The research and questionnaire involve an open-ended or multiple-choice question, it is a quick way to gather data and get results, this covers most of the aspects of the topic. Thus, this will help in creating awareness among the masses about the importance of effective usage of the social platforms and can also develop the thinking process of the students and their critical evaluation aspects to deal with the complex technological aspects. Apart from this, there are some disadvantages: the response is less and does not get a valid response, no personal interaction is present, not reliable for the topic, and researcher biases. In this research, the main disadvantage in data collection is time limitations or time constraints. In this process, researchers do not get valid and various data for this creates difficulty in their research and satisfaction is less with their performance.

Analysis and description of the sample

As stated by Course-Choi & Hammond (2021), the gathered opinion on the issue of social media's influence on the academic aspects of similar age groups has been answered. Thus, taking their specified opinion on the basics of the issues and some portion of the data providers also

indicated personal issues faced by the issue themselves. Hence, asking them a few relevant questions to assess the reliability of their resources and the viability of the authentic answer delivered by them can be located.

In this process, the questions from 2 to 9 mainly focused on assessing the purpose of using the social media platforms by the chosen male and female participants. Apart from that, the chosen sample participants were asked about how long they use different social media platforms, and this data was acquired focusing on each day of a week. The last question of the survey was mainly focused on identifying the perception of the chosen research topic. In this process, it is needed to highlight that the chosen samples were majorly collected from the female students compared to the number of considered male candidates. However, the chosen sample size has been limited to 32 people only due to the lack of time and maintaining a lower complexity of data analysis. The contradictory factors of the opinions gathered from the answers developed for better assessment of executed tests.

There are as many as 17 notable questions enquired from the survey participants and their honest confessions about the topic were taken into the considering factor to develop the model of the discussion and focus on the topic to elaborate on the impacts on the general public on the specific topic to deal with the issue in a rational way. Therefore, taking their ideas of the concerning factor and validating the ideas with data will make the discussion much more effective. Hence, the aspects of the student in the UAE can enable the study to open up about the larger scale of students in the country and their mindset regarding this developed rise of social media usage for their time spending process and techniques (Alaleeli & Alnajjar, 2020).

Factor 1:

Researching purpose	Perception
1	1
1	1
1	1
1	1
1	1
1	1
1	1
1	2
1	2
1	2
1	2
1	2
1	2
1	2
1	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2

2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
3	2
4	2
4	2
4	2

Table 1: Series of researching purpose and perception

(Source: Self-developed)

SUMMARY					
OUTPUT					
Regression Statistics					
Multiple R	0.463383				
R Square	0.214724				
Adjusted R Square	0.188548				
Standard Error	0.378351				
Observations	32				
ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	1.174271	1.174271	8.203125	0.007563
Residual	30	4.294479	0.143149		

Total	31	5.46875						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	1.398773	0.149354	9.36547	2.06E-10	1.093751	1.703795	1.093751	1.703795
Researching purpose	0.214724	0.074971	2.86411	0.007563	0.061614	0.367834	0.061614	0.367834

Table 2: Regression equation

(Source: Self-developed)

RESIDUAL OUTPUT			
Observation	Predicted Perception	Residuals	Standard Residuals
1	1.613497	-0.6135	-1.64831
2	1.613497	-0.6135	-1.64831
3	1.613497	-0.6135	-1.64831
4	1.613497	-0.6135	-1.64831
5	1.613497	-0.6135	-1.64831
6	1.613497	-0.6135	-1.64831
7	1.613497	-0.6135	-1.64831
8	1.613497	0.386503	1.038433
9	1.613497	0.386503	1.038433
10	1.613497	0.386503	1.038433
11	1.613497	0.386503	1.038433
12	1.613497	0.386503	1.038433
13	1.613497	0.386503	1.038433
14	1.613497	0.386503	1.038433

15	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
16	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
17	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
18	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
19	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
20	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
21	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
22	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
23	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
24	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
25	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
26	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
27	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
28	1.828221	0.171779	0.461526
29	2.042945	-0.04294	-0.11538
30	2.257669	-0.25767	-0.69229
31	2.257669	-0.25767	-0.69229

32	2.257669	-0.25767	-0.69229
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Table 3: Residual output

(Source: Self-developed)

PROBABILITY OUTPUT	
Percentile	Perception
1.5625	1
4.6875	1
7.8125	1
10.9375	1
14.0625	1
17.1875	1
20.3125	1
23.4375	2
26.5625	2
29.6875	2
32.8125	2
35.9375	2
39.0625	2
42.1875	2

45.3125	2
48.4375	2
51.5625	2
54.6875	2
57.8125	2
60.9375	2
64.0625	2
67.1875	2
70.3125	2
73.4375	2
76.5625	2
79.6875	2
82.8125	2
85.9375	2
89.0625	2
92.1875	2
95.3125	2

98.4375	2
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Table 4: Probability output

(Source: Self-developed)

The above tables are mainly formed to evaluate the applicability of H1 or hypothesis one. For this purpose, questions 1 to 9 have been considered. These questions were particularly focused on evaluating for what purposes social media platforms are being used by the UAE students. Considering the findings, it has been identified that the *Significance Of* value from Regression test came to be 0.007563. Apart from that, the *P-value* for using social media platforms could be identified to be 0.007563. Thus, a minimal or negligible relation of using social media purposes and the perception of the participants could be observed. Based on these findings it can be stated that there is no direct relationship present between the purpose of using social media and the academic performance of the students.

Factor 2:

3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
3	2
4	2
4	2
4	2

4	2
4	2
4	2
4	2
4	2

Table 5: Series of time consumption and perception

(Source: Self-developed)

SUMMARY OUTPUT						
Regression Statistics						
Multiple R	0.659112501					
R Square	0.434429289					
Adjusted R Square	0.415576932					
Standard Error	0.321090061					
Observations	32					
ANOVA						
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F	

Regression	1	2.3757851						
n	1	76	2.375785	23.04377	4.09E-05			
Residual	30	3.0929648						
	24	0.103099						
Total	31	5.46875						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	0.9120603	0.1897547			0.5245293	1.2995912	0.5245293	1.2995912
	02	81	4.806521	4.02E-05	4	63	4	63
TIME								
CONSUMPTION	0.3090452	0.0643791			0.1775654	0.4405250	0.1775654	0.4405250
	26	62	4.800392	4.09E-05	38	15	38	15

Table 6: Regression equation

(Source: Self-developed)

RESIDUAL OUTPUT			
Observation	Predicted PERCEPTION	Residuals	Standard Residuals
1	1.221105528	-0.221105528	-0.69999
2	1.221105528	-0.221105528	-0.69999
3	1.530150754	-0.530150754	-1.67839
4	1.530150754	-0.530150754	-1.67839
5	1.530150754	-0.530150754	-1.67839
6	1.530150754	-0.530150754	-1.67839
7	1.530150754	-0.530150754	-1.67839
8	1.530150754	0.469849246	1.487483
9	1.530150754	0.469849246	1.487483
10	1.530150754	0.469849246	1.487483
11	1.530150754	0.469849246	1.487483
12	1.530150754	0.469849246	1.487483
13	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085

14	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
15	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
16	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
17	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
18	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
19	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
20	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
21	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
22	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
23	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
24	1.83919598	0.16080402	0.509085
25	2.148241206	-0.148241206	-0.46931
26	2.148241206	-0.148241206	-0.46931
27	2.148241206	-0.148241206	-0.46931
28	2.148241206	-0.148241206	-0.46931
29	2.148241206	-0.148241206	-0.46931
30	2.148241206	-0.148241206	-0.46931

31	2.148241206	-0.148241206	-0.46931
32	2.148241206	-0.148241206	-0.46931

Table 7: Residual output

(Source: Self-developed)

PROBABILITY OUTPUT	
Percentile	PERCEPTION
1.5625	1
4.6875	1
7.8125	1
10.9375	1
14.0625	1
17.1875	1
20.3125	1
23.4375	2
26.5625	2
29.6875	2
32.8125	2
35.9375	2
39.0625	2
42.1875	2

45.3125	2
48.4375	2
51.5625	2
54.6875	2
57.8125	2
60.9375	2
64.0625	2
67.1875	2
70.3125	2
73.4375	2
76.5625	2
79.6875	2
82.8125	2
85.9375	2
89.0625	2
92.1875	2
95.3125	2

98.4375	2
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Table 8: Probability output

(Source: Self-developed)

The above tables have focused on testing the hypothesis relevant for question 10 to 16 which is evaluating whether there is any relationship present between duration of social media platforms with the academic performance level. Based on the findings the *P-value* has been estimated to be 0.0000409 whereas based on regression test results the value of *Significance F* observed to be 0.0000409136. This means that the null hypothesis here could be rejected. In other terms, the duration of using social media platforms does not create a direct influence on the performance level.

Factor 3:

2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
2	2
3	2
3	2
4	2
4	2
4	2
4	2
4	2

Table 9: Series of Performance enhancement and perception

(Source: Self-developed)

SUMMARY					
OUTPUT					
Regression Statistics					
Multiple R	0.651534				
R Square	0.424496				
Adjusted R Square	0.405313				
Standard Error	0.323897				
Observations	32				
ANOVA					
	df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Regression	1	2.321463	2.321463	22.12823	5.37E-05
Residual	30	3.147287	0.10491		

Total	31	5.46875						
	Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%	Lower 95.0%	Upper 95.0%
Intercept	1.162791	0.1434	8.1087	4.73E-09	0.869928	1.455653	0.869928	1.455653
performance enhancement	0.286822	0.060973	4.704066	5.37E-05	0.162298	0.411345	0.162298	0.411345

Table 10: Regression equation

(Source: Self-developed)

RESIDUAL OUTPUT			
Observation	Predicted Perception	Residuals	Standard Residuals
1	1.449612	-0.44961	-1.41108
2	1.449612	-0.44961	-1.41108
3	1.449612	-0.44961	-1.41108
4	1.449612	-0.44961	-1.41108
5	1.449612	-0.44961	-1.41108
6	1.449612	-0.44961	-1.41108
7	1.449612	-0.44961	-1.41108
8	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
9	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
10	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
11	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
12	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
13	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
14	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184

15	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
16	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
17	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
18	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
19	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
20	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
21	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
22	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
23	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
24	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
25	1.736434	0.263566	0.827184
26	2.023256	-0.02326	-0.07299
27	2.023256	-0.02326	-0.07299
28	2.310078	-0.31008	-0.97316
29	2.310078	-0.31008	-0.97316
30	2.310078	-0.31008	-0.97316
31	2.310078	-0.31008	-0.97316

32	2.310078	-0.31008	-0.97316
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Table 11: Residual output

(Source: Self-developed)

PROBABILITY OUTPUT	
Percentile	Perception
1.5625	1
4.6875	1
7.8125	1
10.9375	1
14.0625	1
17.1875	1
20.3125	1
23.4375	2
26.5625	2
29.6875	2
32.8125	2
35.9375	2
39.0625	2
42.1875	2

45.3125	2
48.4375	2
51.5625	2
54.6875	2
57.8125	2
60.9375	2
64.0625	2
67.1875	2
70.3125	2
73.4375	2
76.5625	2
79.6875	2
82.8125	2
85.9375	2
89.0625	2
92.1875	2
95.3125	2

98.4375	2
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Table 12: Probability output

(Source: Self-developed)

The above estimations have focused on showing the interrelationships or correlation of perception and academic performance of the students in the UAE. In this process, the results highlighted that students hold a positive aspect relating to the influence of social media on overall academic performance. This means that the participants hold it true that a positive influence is made by social media on their academic performance level and hence it satisfies the H3.

Discussion, recommendation, and Implications

In the first factor, the time-consuming aspects of the 32 participants in the survey put their opinions on the basis the time consumption and perception of the topics is taken into consideration. Thus, the effectiveness of each aspect and its effects on the perception made are dependent on the trends. The regression statistics show an observation of 32 participants and the adjusted r-square valuation is 0.415 for the method of computing the sampling process with proper effectiveness. However, during this calculation Significance, F has formulated a 4.09 valuation. Therefore, the configuration process can be denoted as impactful on the aspects of the social media factors in the study portion from the evaluation done on the basis of this factor. Thus, following the manner of social media will surely have its way to printing the better academic performances of the country over a longer period of time. Therefore, the performance of the students does depend on the P-value of 4.09. Thus, limiting the consumption of social media will have an effect on the academic proportion of a certain age group and their academic presentations as well.

In factor 2 the determining aspects of the discussion were set on two vital sections of researching the purpose and perception of the crowd to deal with the issue and its effective measures in order to enhance their performance. Thus, improving the perception of the social media aspirations of the students will be dependent on the research tools as well. The 32 participants showed their views on the basis of their research method and the impact of such methods to cause effective implications on the academic sectors. Adjusted r square valuation of this factor shows a numbering of 0.188 and significance F of this 0.0075. Therefore, its effectiveness for the research purpose shows its evaluation process to enhance the chances of developing a better education structure in the country in recent time to make better academic performances for all sections of the students. Thus, the P-factor of the research purpose on the basis of social media usage shows a valuation of 0.0075 for the time period. Hence, locating the right area to improve the academic abilities of the students in-country is quite essential for educational development.

Form factor 3, performance enhancement of the students on the basis of their social media perception has been taken into consideration to deal with the concerning issue and its implications of the issue's long-term effects. However, in this process, the evaluation followed step-by-step analytical proceedings to measure the impact of the performance improvements of the students in UAE with the alignment of the social media perception and its effective mannerism. Thus, the adjusted r-square of the evaluation showed a valuation of 0.405 among the 32 observations and their vies on the basis of the study's requirement to answer the critical analysis from the core of the analytical display. Hence, focusing on the different approaches taken by each member and their values of the social media perceptions. Therefore, the significance F of the valuation is indicating a numbering of 5.37 in this observation period. Thus, the condition can be considered effective for the perception values set for a larger scale of

audiences and their ability to deal with the social media aspects to enhance their values and more so the valuable prospect of academic development. As mentioned by Alghizzawi et al. (2019), Although there are few backlashes of these social media usage if used in a right and methodical way they are meant to impact the education system with its beneficial values massively.

Recommendations

The usage of social media depends on the user and its values to make proper utilization of the resources to make the process of learning easier for themselves and their educators as well. Due to the large scale of the data available in the social world following the right direction to focus and make amends of the available data for the right reason needs to be taught to the pupils of the UAE should be one of the top priorities for the teachers. However, an indication is only a suggestion, following the path is completely dependent on the motives of the student and their academic development process. Thus, improvising the tool at disposal to maximize the education proceedings are required to be followed and executed with proper efficiency (Lwakatare, Raj, Crnkovic, Bosch & Olsson, 2020). Hence, the academic system can get a major boost from the beneficial structure of the web portals by assigning the students the best possible articles, journals, and books to enhance their skills and knowledge about academic perceptions.

Also, another section of the education process is getting a better and broader view of the academic curriculums for the teachers as well. Teachers can improve their modular aspects with a better proportion of the education portals. Massive up-gradation in the current structure of internet usage in the country can be done by enlightening the audiences about the brighter side of the social media platforms and their effectiveness from the ground levels to the executive aspirations of the academic developments. Similarly, the focus should be on the improvement of the student's perception about catching productive prospects from the business to enhance their

outlook from the educational purposes to get a better evaluation of themselves. Thus, the focus of the education level should be inclusive of the logistical aspects of the education systems on the basis of the structural evaluation.

Implications

The academic upgradations of the social media tools on the basis of the education section to deal with the proper functions of the consumers and their ability to utilize the information effectively. Thus, instructing the students of the UAE to develop a better sense of AI proceedings with an eye on the possibilities of revolutionizing the current study structure (Ahmed, 2020). The prospect of these major improvements should start from the base and develop the creative mindset for the students to get better processing of the social platforms to enhance their understanding level for better implications in the education system. Creating awareness among the masses about the importance of effective usage of the social platforms can also develop the thinking process of the students and their critical evaluation aspects to deal with the complex technological aspects. Therefore, implementing the recent trends in the logistical sections will ensure proper usage of the information gathered from the web portals in the assignments of the students to let them prepare better projects. Also, teachers can make sure proper evaluation of the student's academic proportions is followed here. Hence, education portals of the country can develop their own process to deal with the function of the educational values. Therefore, following the latest trends of the study modules in the global platforms through the web portals and social media sectors can be denoted to improve the structure with the proper mix of logistical help that enhance the education industry of the nation massively.

Conclusion

Limitations

The research was done in a way to make the proper execution of the functions to ensure the process is efficient and perfectly managed. Thus, identifying the limitations of the stuffy is needed to make the adjustments effective. Hence, the testing process follows a singular research aspect with the inclusion of a certain number of people, and their values are taken into consideration to mention their thoughts about the study. Therefore, getting collective answers from the queries is hard to get for the total assumption of the study. Hence, following this solution just based on the study proportion means the view of the project is one-sided.

The resources gathered to convey the survey are quite limited in the mannerisms and the prospect of such aspects is also quite narrow. Therefore, setting a study for a larger portion of the crowd about the academic efficiency in the country is a backward step, to be honest. Thus, the productive measures or the effectiveness of the terms are based on a few people and their own singular perspective of this global perspective aspect. Hence, completely relying on the data from the sampling technique is not the ideal process to get to the ideal answer to this complex process.

The test is based on the limited reachability just on the basis of the UAE localities and omits the transformation of these data from the global perspective. Therefore, these data are quite limited in their nature and focus on just a specific platform for the parameter of the academic system in the country and its effectiveness from social media perceptions is making the study harder for the general people to get a rationalized view of the prospect. However, a proper view of the study can be generated from the test and further improvements in the specific areas are needed to get a better understanding of the situation of the country.

Future research

In the above study, the researcher does primary research through primary data but in the future, we need to do secondary research for doing secondary research to help the researcher find out the gap in primary research and after that, help to overcome this gap and make the research successful. In this, the sample size is only 32 students but, in the future, a need to take a large population and also take school and college students to increase the sample size. This helps the researcher to get various types of data and through this, they can create proper justification for the research. In the present research, they only focus on learning through social media but in the future, they want to sift their learning in digital platforms for getting better results. The researcher's social media has a negative effect on academic perspectives that many people are addicted to social media, and excessive use of social media leads to addiction this is the main reason for distraction from their education. At the time of social media, many students are lost or unable to focus on their studies during their teaching sessions. Therefore, they use to waste time scrolling and watching newsfeeds and uploading posts on social media. Socialization is helping to make the distance between their friends. Therefore, setting a study for a larger portion of the crowd about the academic efficiency in the country is a backward step, to be honest. This has a negative impact on the education sector, and they lose the relationship with their beloved person. Through this social media, the student faced cyberbullying is harmful to them and provide inappropriate content for their learning and development in the process. In social media, they face some fake news which hampered education. Sometimes the content presents on social media that are inappropriate for the students. Social media is across geographical limitations for this it limited their learning process. The research is on basis of the UAE localities and omits the transformation of these data from the global perspective. Therefore, these data are quite limited

in their nature and focus on just a specific platform for the parameter of the academic system in the country and its effectiveness from social media perceptions is making the study harder for the general people to get a rationalized view of the prospect.

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Appendix

Q1. gender	Male Female
Q2.I use social media to make new friends	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree
Q3. I chat with my friends using social media	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree
Q4.When I want to upload my pictures and videos, I make use of social media ?	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree
Q5.I research on my assignments and read educational articles using social media	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree

Q6. I stay up to date with latest trends and news with the help of social media	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree
Q7. When I want to research about future academic careers, I simply use social media	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree
Q8. I engage in social media to reach out to my teachers	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree
Q9. Social media help me reach out to my classmates for group assignments easily	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree
Q10. I am in social media groups like Whatsapp and Facebook groups	Strongly disagree Disagree Agree Strongly agree

Q11.How many hours do you spend on social media on Monday?	0 1-2 2-4 4-6 more than 6 hours
Q12.How many hours do you spend on social media on Tuesday?	0 1-2 2-4 4-6 more than 6 hours
Q 13.How many hours do you spend on social media on wednesday?	0 1-2 2-4 4-6 more than 6 hours
Q 14.How many hours do you spend on social media on Thursday?	0 1-2 2-4 4-6 more than 6 hours

Q17. How many hours do you spend on social media on Friday?	0 1-2 2-4 4-6 more than 6 hours
Q17.Q16.How many hours do you spend on social media on Saturday?	0 1-2 2-4 4-6 more than 6 hours
Q18.How many hours do you spend on social media on Sunday?	0 1-2 2-4 4-6 more than 6 hours
Q19. What is your perception of Social Media on your academic performance?	Socail media help me improve my academic performance. Socail media affect my academic performance negatively.